

GLOBALIZATION AND THE ACCEPTANCE OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN OUR LIVES AND IN ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

Purpose – *This paper brings arguments for the acceptance and applicability of the new technologies as basis for globalization and organizations' market performance improvement.*

Methodology/approach – *Questionnaire based research was performed on a sample of 363 Romanian respondents. Different approaches regarding the research subject were defined and tested using SPSS. Exploratory factor analysis was used to define classes of reasons for not implementing the new technologies and groups of training areas that would increase work performance.*

Findings – *The main conclusion shows a positive perception and willingness of respondents to use the new technologies. High costs and lack of training are the main reasons, according to the respondents, that make the use of the new technologies difficult.*

Research limitations/implications – *The research was not random, it was based on reasoning, because, due to the time it took to perform the research, it would have been difficult to identify the available respondents based on a random sampling.*

Practical implications – *This paper points out some of the human resources management's challenges and the importance of the training programs, in order to prepare people and organizations to handle the use of the new and complex technologies.*

Originality/value – *This research leads to useful recommendations for the human resources management, in the context of adopting the new technologies in order to improve the organizational performances.*

Key words: *statistical analysis, human resources, abilities of the future.*

Introduction

The term globalization has multiple meanings, referring to multidimensional and complex processes-economical, cultural and political. As Erixon (2018) points out, "globalization means different things to different people", having a social and economic impact by "expanding the role for trade, foreign direct investment and other forms of cross-border exchange in national economies". Globalization may also refer to "the transfer, adjustment and development of values, knowledge, technology and behavioral norms across countries and societies in different parts of the world" (Cheng, 2003 apud Rifai, 2013).

Globalization means the use of the new technologies, developed to sustain people's and organizations' integration and interconnectivity worldwide. If, a century ago, it was not common for people to choose workplaces in companies far away from their homes, nowadays, distance is no longer an issue. Let us imagine an employee working for a company situated at a considerable distance from his home. The company provides transportation to the workplace and makes available technologies that would allow him to work, if necessary, from a distance. Furthermore, his home is equipped with sensors that allow handling and monitoring a series of home appliances from a distance. As an example, using different remotely controlled technologies one may start, at a specified time, the heating or ventilation system, wash laundry, clean-up, monitor the fridge supplies and send orders to selected shops.

Regarding the use of the new technologies in organizations, in the context of a crisis such as the current COVID-19 sanitary crisis, the company may be interested in monitoring the employees' access and involvement at his workplace, when he works remotely. The collaborative robots and the new technologies based on artificial intelligence (biometrics and voice recognition technologies) are viable solutions, especially in this context.

Further, we intend to present two categories of arguments that emphasize the human resource's role and determines us to consider accepting and implementing the new technologies as a support for globalization and organizations' market performance improvement.

A. Technologies and human resources: facets of globalization

Discussing about the globalization's direct and indirect effects on a country's technological capacity and on the degree to which technology is used in economy, Erixon (2018) points out among the benefits: (1) the possibility of importing technologies that countries could not otherwise produce on their own or for which they would have to make great efforts in order to copy and (2) the stimulation of productivity of some activity sectors, due to the investments of the multinational organizations. As regards the adoption of new technology, globalization represents an extremely important framework that allows their rapid spread on the markets, in organizations and in the lives of people from different countries.

Production factors, factors that determine the product's or service's costs, determine the configuration of the businesses' operation system. Regarding the economic globalization, Ruettimann (2014) suggests a model consisting of five typologies, one of which refers to the human resource – "comparative competencies of the labor force". This type of globalization takes into consideration "the level of available skills", the costs involved in using them and "the cost for transferring that service to a lower costs economy".

From the perspective of the costs involved in using the labor force's competences, Romania is known as a low-cost economy, compared to other European countries. The situation in which Romanian employees work for companies with headquarters in different parts of the world is more and more common, a significant contribution being brought by the use of the information and communications technology. In order to maintain competitiveness, companies need to take into consideration the continuous development of the production factors, and in the decision process regarding the use of the new technology, it should be analyzed the level to which the cultural factor influences the acceptance of these technologies into work.

B. Technologies and human resources: contribution to the organization's market performance

A bibliographic study on human capital measurement and the influence of the human resource on organizational performances (Mayo, 2014) shows its direct influences on profitability, productivity, market value growth and sales. The influence of the human resource can be seen in areas such as: staff commitment, staff continuous development, with emphasis on communication, change management and employees' involvement in the decision-making processes. Another aspect that leads to a higher financial and market performance and to a higher competitiveness is the introduction of new ideas and technology, as shown in a study regarding the use of the new IoT technology in the value chain of some Hungarian companies (Nagy et al., 2018). The implementation of the new technology contributes directly to the creating of new jobs, to work productivity growth and to the efficient use of resources. It also leads to the need of investing in people by developing abilities and educational programs that would prepare the human resource to handle the challenges of the future.

Research problem

At an international and European level, in countries such as Finland or Germany, the new technologies are frequently used both inside companies and in the private life. In Romania and countries similar to it from the development point of view, it has been observed an openness to the use of the new technology,

especially by people with high income. Still, there may be less information available and the public may have less access to the technological news.

In order to grow the extent to which we use the new technology in our life, the target audience should first be convinced of its positive and sustainable impact and then informed and trained to use it. For this, research is needed in order to identify the reasons for which people would consider difficult to use the new technology and once these barriers are identified, they should be removed through education and training. There will be, most certainly, the need for new abilities for the employees in the future and new continuing education programs should be developed.

Research aim and methodology

The research focused on identifying particular aspects related to: (1) the respondents' interest in using the new technology in order to increase work performance, (2) the level to which respondents are generally open to the idea of using the new technology, (3) the causes that would make difficult the use of the new technology at the workplace, (4) the respondents' perception of the competences that describe the "employee of the future" and (5) the training areas necessary to increase work performance.

Three categories of exploratory investigation were set, aiming: (1) the identification of general aspects related to the respondents' interest in using the new technology in order to increase work performance, (2) the identification of general aspects regarding the accommodation with the new 4.0 technology (the need of performance focused trainings and the respondents' perception of the assimilation of the new technology) and (3) the identification of the latent factors in adopting the new technology and training the employees in order to increase performance.

Hypotheses regarding the research theme were drawn for the study, the null hypotheses are marked with $H_{01} - H_{011}$, and the alternative hypotheses with $H_{11} - H_{111}$. The survey was used as a method and the questionnaire as an instrument for gathering information, being sent online, using <http://www.isondaje.ro> The hypotheses have been tested using SPSS. Factor analysis was used to analyze the data.

The research was performed on a sample of 363 respondents. A non-random research method, based on reasoning, was used to select the subjects. Taking into consideration the non-random sampling, we cannot see it as a 5% limited acceptable error and a 95% level of trust research, the results being valid at a sample level.

Figure 1. Respondents' profile

Figure 1 presents the profile of the investigated respondent: feminine respondent, group age 20-35 years old, who experienced teleworking as an employee.

The investigated sample may be layered in layers represented by "respondents' groups from the areas of activity". The respondents were students (25%) and employees (61%) who work in fields like: education – teachers (~11%), IT industry (7%), manufacturing industry and other industries (14%), administrative services (5,5%), other areas of activity (represented by less than 5%). Approximately 14 percent of the respondents didn't agree to offer information related to gender, age, activity, being included as "unreported" in the SPSS data base used to interpret the information.

Findings

A. The use of the new technology

Main results, presented in Table 1, show that:

- (1) more than 80% of the respondents are interested in using the new technology in order to improve their work performance; weak negative correlations, significant at the 0,01 level, with the field of activity and the age group have been identified,
- (2) the level to which respondents are, in general, open to the use of the new technology is a little above average,
- (3) high costs and lack of training are the main reasons that make the use of the new technology at the workplace, difficult.

Table 1. Confirmed hypotheses regarding the use of the new technology

<p>H₀₁: More than 80% of the respondents are interested in using the new technology in order to improve their work performance.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Respondents are interested in using the new technology in order to improve their work performance</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; margin-top: 10px;"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid Yes</td> <td style="text-align: center;">291</td> <td style="text-align: center;">80.2</td> <td style="text-align: center;">80.2</td> <td style="text-align: center;">80.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> <td style="text-align: center;">18</td> <td style="text-align: center;">5.0</td> <td style="text-align: center;">5.0</td> <td style="text-align: center;">85.1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>I don't know / I didn't think</td> <td style="text-align: center;">54</td> <td style="text-align: center;">14.9</td> <td style="text-align: center;">14.9</td> <td style="text-align: center;">100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td style="text-align: center;">363</td> <td style="text-align: center;">100.0</td> <td style="text-align: center;">100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Yes	291	80.2	80.2	80.2	No	18	5.0	5.0	85.1	I don't know / I didn't think	54	14.9	14.9	100.0	Total	363	100.0	100.0																					
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The respondents were asked to check, in the list, the reasons why it should be considered difficult adopting the new technologies at work, multiple answers being possible. The question offered the respondents the possibility of giving also other reasons than the ones suggested. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Other reasons that make adopting the new technologies at work difficult

In order to identify the latent factors in the process of adopting the new technologies, the exploratory factor analysis was used, in order to reduce the number of the specified reasons.

The KMO and Bartlett test, applied to determine if the partial correlations between the used variables are small, has the value of 0,584 (>0,5), which shows that the variables will group according to the factors and the factor analysis is suitable for the variables included in the research. The Extraction values from the Communalities table are >0,3.

As a result of the first analysis there are three factors that explain 52% of the total variation. The analysis has been redone, requesting the identification of 4 factors, representing 65% of the total variation. The Eigenvalues for each of the four factors can be seen in the table related to total variation. Out of the factors selected as being latent in adopting the new technologies at work, the four factors explain a rate of 19, 16, 15 and 15 percent.

The solution of interpretation of the latent factors, using the factors' rotation Varimax method, is plotted in Figure 3.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.584
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	62.792
	df	21
	Sig.	.000

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.493	21.324	21.324	1.493	21.324	21.324	1.337	19.097	19.097
2	1.135	16.219	37.543	1.135	16.219	37.543	1.147	16.385	35.482
3	1.009	14.419	51.962	1.009	14.419	51.962	1.069	15.275	50.757
4	.934	13.344	65.305	.934	13.344	65.305	1.018	14.548	65.305
5	.891	12.722	78.027						
6	.807	11.524	89.551						
7	.731	10.449	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
R1_lack of information	1.000	.813
R2_lack of instructions for use	1.000	.450
R3_lack of training	1.000	.642
R4_fear of making mistakes	1.000	.606
R5_fear of change	1.000	.573
R6_fear of being monitored	1.000	.941
R7_high costs	1.000	.547

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Component Score Coefficient Matrix

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
R1_lack of information	-.088	-.005	.859	-.040
R2_lack of instructions for use	.410	-.006	.210	-.040
R3_lack of training	.592	-.225	-.100	.154
R4_fear of making mistakes	-.015	.606	.285	.102
R5_fear of change	-.063	.636	-.189	-.043
R6_fear of being monitored	-.018	.030	-.041	.952
R7_high costs	-.501	-.234	.238	.199

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Figure 3. Graphic representation of the four factors extracted after the rotation, corresponding to the reasons that lead to not adopting the new technologies

B. The abilities that describe the “employee of the future”

The results show that, from the respondents’ perspective, the „employee of the future” has to be adaptable to change, creative and connected (Table 2). A few of the remarks regarding the ranking of the “abilities of the future”, performed on groups of respondents, are presented in Figure 4.

Table 2. Confirmed hypotheses regarding the abilities that describe the „employee of the future”

		Statistics				
		Creative	Connected (networking)	Communicative	Assertive (open with people)	Adaptable (open to change)
N	Valid	363	363	363	363	363
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.88	3.05	3.15	3.10	2.81
Std. Deviation		1.514	1.344	1.233	1.385	1.551
Skewness		.111	-.027	-.108	-.126	.222
Std. Error of Skewness		.128	.128	.128	.128	.128
Kurtosis		-1.446	-1.145	-1.010	-1.241	-1.466
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.255	.255	.255	.255	.255
Sum		1046	1108	1143	1127	1021

Characteristics ranking – on age groups

- 20-35 years old: adaptable, connected and assertive, creative
- over 55 years old: creative and connected, communicative

Report

Mean

Age group	Creative	Connected (networking)	Communicative	Assertive (open with people)	Adaptable (open to change)
unreported	2.64	2.98	3.00	3.56	2.82
below 20	3.17	2.67	3.17	3.08	2.92
between 20 - 35	3.05	2.99	3.15	2.99	2.82
between 36 - 45	2.71	3.29	3.38	3.07	2.55
between 46 - 55	2.58	3.28	3.15	3.11	2.87
above 55	2.91	2.91	3.00	3.09	3.09
Total	2.88	3.05	3.15	3.10	2.81

Characteristics ranking – on gender layers

- Male: adaptable, assertive, creative
- Female: creative, adaptable, connected

Report

Mean

Gender	Creative	Connected (networking)	Communicative	Assertive (open with people)	Adaptable (open to change)
unreported	2.64	2.98	3.00	3.56	2.82
male	3.06	3.17	3.23	2.91	2.62
female	2.87	3.03	3.15	3.07	2.88
Total	2.88	3.05	3.15	3.10	2.81

Characteristics that describe the “employee of the future” – averages, on areas of activity

Report

Mean

Field of activity	Creative	Connected (networking)	Communicative	Assertive (open with people)	Adaptable (open to change)
unreported	2.64	2.98	3.00	3.56	2.82
education - student	3.23	3.03	3.12	2.90	2.71
education - teacher	3.00	2.97	3.03	2.87	3.13
IT industry	2.96	3.15	3.27	3.23	2.38
manufacturing	2.50	3.10	2.90	3.50	3.00
other industries	2.55	2.75	3.35	3.38	2.98
transport and logistics	3.50	1.50	5.00	2.00	3.00
construcții	4.00	2.50	3.25	3.75	1.50
public administration and defense	2.56	2.94	3.33	2.94	3.22
administrative and other services	2.45	3.75	3.15	3.15	2.50
financial - banking	2.14	3.71	3.71	2.43	3.00
juridic	2.14	4.00	3.14	2.43	3.29
management	2.71	2.71	3.14	3.57	2.86
marketing	3.00	1.00	4.00	5.00	2.00
trade	3.18	2.82	3.12	3.18	2.71
entrepreneurship	3.57	3.57	2.71	2.43	2.71
health and social assistance	3.00	3.83	3.33	2.50	2.33
other areas of activity	2.91	3.00	2.82	3.09	3.18
Total	2.88	3.05	3.15	3.10	2.81

H07: More than 60% of the respondents place in “top 3 characteristics of the employee of the future”: adaptable, connected and creative.

Adaptable (open to change)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1-st place	106	29.2	29.2	29.2
2-nd place	73	20.1	20.1	49.3
3-rd place	52	14.3	14.3	63.6
4-th place	47	12.9	12.9	76.6
5-th place	85	23.4	23.4	100.0
Total	363	100.0	100.0	

Connected (networking)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1-st place	59	16.3	16.3	16.3
2-nd place	72	19.8	19.8	36.1
3-rd place	92	25.3	25.3	61.4
4-th place	71	19.6	19.6	81.0
5-th place	69	19.0	19.0	100.0
Total	363	100.0	100.0	

Creative (solving complex problems)					
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid 1-st place	98	27.0	27.0	27.0	
2-nd place	66	18.2	18.2	45.2	
3-rd place	59	16.3	16.3	61.4	
4-th place	61	16.8	16.8	78.2	
5-th place	79	21.8	21.8	100.0	
Total	363	100.0	100.0		

Remarks regarding the ranking of the “abilities of the future”

- The group of students rank “creativity” as number one.
- The group of teachers rank “assertiveness” as number one.
- The group of respondents from “manufacturing and other industries” rank “creativity” as number one.
- The group of respondents age between 20-35 rank “assertiveness” as number two.
- The group of respondents age above 55 rank “creativity” as number one.
- More than 40% of the respondents from the “IT industry” no matter the gender, rank “adaptability” as number one.
- None of the feminine respondents from the “IT industry” ranks “creativity” as number one.

Figure 4. Differences in the “abilities of the future” ranking

C. Training areas in order to increase performance

The results show that more than 50% of the respondents consider training for “technological novelty” as useful in improving their work performance (Table 3). In order to identify the latent factors in performance-enhancing trainings, exploratory factor analysis was used to reduce the number of training fields mentioned in the questionnaire.

Table 3. Confirmed hypotheses regarding the training areas in order to increase performance

The KMO and Bartlett test, applied to determine if the partial correlations between the used variables are small, has the value of 0,596 (>0,5), which shows that the variables will group according to the factors and the factor analysis is suitable for the variables included in the research. The Extraction values from the Communalities table are >0,3.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.596
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	152.904
	df	21
	Sig.	.000

Component Score Coefficient Matrix

	Component		
	1	2	3
C1_Technological novelty	-.135	.554	.008
C2_Innovation and creativity	-.210	-.102	.758
C3_Work-life balance	.475	-.069	-.069
C4_Health and vitality	.303	-.181	.318
C5_Overwork avoidance	.464	.137	-.181
C6_Human relations management	.197	.171	.391
C7_Managing the human-technology relationship	.118	.654	-.122

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
C1_Technological novelty	1.000	.549
C2_Innovation and creativity	1.000	.749
C3_Work-life balance	1.000	.560
C4_Health and vitality	1.000	.493
C5_Overwork avoidance	1.000	.503
C6_Human relations management	1.000	.544
C7_Managing the human-technology relationship	1.000	.640

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.690	24.141	24.141	1.690	24.141	24.141	1.584	22.629	22.629
2	1.399	19.983	44.124	1.399	19.983	44.124	1.250	17.858	40.488
3	.950	13.567	57.691	.950	13.567	57.691	1.204	17.203	57.691
4	.856	12.235	69.926						
5	.792	11.311	81.237						
6	.704	10.063	91.300						
7	.609	8.700	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Figure 5. Graphic representation of the three factors extracted after the rotation, corresponding to training areas for work performance-enhancing

As a result of the first analysis we identified two factors that explain 44 % of the total variation. The analysis has been redone, requesting the identification of 3 factors. The Eigenvalues for each of the three factors can be seen in the table related to total variation. The three factors explain a rate of 58 percent of the total variation of all noted variables. The solution of interpretation of the latent factors, using the factors' rotation Varimax method, is plotted in Figure 5.

Discussion and conclusions

As it was argued in the first part of this paper, globalization leads to the growth of a country's or organization's technological capacity by adopting the new technologies. As far as the preparation of the human resource towards this development approach is concerned, the first step is accepting the new technologies and then implementing them in the organizations.

When making investments in order to enhance companies' technological capacity, human resources management should take into consideration aspects such as: (1) training the decision makers so that they can have access to the technological novelties, (2) training the employees so that they accept and

use the new technologies and (3) promoting the contribution of the new technology to the growth of organizational performance, despite the high costs involved.

This paper identifies four classes of reasons, latent factors in the process of implementing the new technologies in work (Figure 6) and three groups of continuing education programs, latent factors in training for performance-enhancement (Figure 7), by the investigated respondents. It can be noted that some of the respondents declare that they are opened to the use of the new technology, not having any reasons to fear, but there are also respondents that emphasize people's need of human interaction and a limited acceptance of the new technologies, for data processing. Other barriers mentioned, are the possible opposition of the management to the acceptance of the new technologies or the fear that the technology provider cannot ensure the security of the information requested to the users, a possible data leakage being able to occur.

<i>Latent factors in the process of implementing the new technologies in work</i>			
1. educational reasons	2. emotional reasons	3. educational and financial reasons	4. emotional reasons
lack of instructions	fear of change	lack of information	fear of being monitored
lack of training	fear of making mistakes	high costs	

Figure 6. Possible barriers in the process of implementing the new technologies in work

<i>Latent factors in training for performance-enhancement</i>		
Vitality management	Ergonomics and technological novelty	Creativity and communication
Work-life balance	Managing human technology relationship	Innovation and creativity
Overwork avoidance	Technological novelty	Human relations management
Health and vitality		Health and vitality

Figure 7. Continuing education programs for performance-enhancement

Most certainly, new abilities will be necessary in the future for the employees and new continuing education programs need to be developed. More than 60% of the investigated respondents noted in the “top 3 characteristics of the employee of the future” adaptability, creativity and connecting capability.

This paper's main conclusion shows a positive perception and openness to the use of the new technologies of the investigated Romanian respondents. It also emphasizes some challenges for the human resources management and the need for developing some training programs in order to prepare people and organizations to handle the use of the new and complex technologies.

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